

COMMITMENT, JOB SATISFACTION, TEAMWORK, AND TRAINING ON PRODUCTIVITY OF EMPLOYEES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Teamwork, and Training on Productivity of Employees in Higher Education Institution

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Abstract

For any business to serve and satisfy both customers and employees, employee productivity is essential. Leveraging the full potential of their workforce, ensuring long-term gains in productivity, and fostering a culture of ongoing improvement for the purpose of attaining organizational excellence. This study seeks to describe the level of employees' commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training on productivity. After scientific validation and reliability tests, questionnaires were used as data-gathering tools. Data for this descriptive correlational and causal research design was employed for the study and purposive sampling was done in choosing the participants gathered from the 518 staff and faculty members in Higher Education Institution. Results revealed that employee productivity was positively correlated with other variables, indicating that high productivity levels were associated with higher levels of commitment, job satisfaction, effective teamwork, and training initiative benefits. Nonetheless, Higher Education employees' productivity is significantly influenced by teamwork and training. This means that when there is teamwork among the employees and top management, and employees are provided with relevant training, employees' productivity will significantly increase.

Keywords: *employee productivity in higher education institution, teamwork in higher education institution, trainings in higher education institution, productivity of employees in higher education institution*

Introduction

In the ever-changing world of modern work environments, the idea of worker productivity has taken center stage for companies that looked to boost productivity and attain long-term expansion. Workers' productivity, which was commonly expressed as output per unit of input, was a complex concept that was impacted by several variables, including personal traits, company culture, and external environmental conditions.

A corporate culture that placed faces demands on employees' time, leading to burnout, inadequate efforts to engage and motivate employees in their roles, outdated or poorly designed performance evaluation processes, failure to provide employees with the necessary tools, resources, and up-to-date technology, and poor compensation were some of the problems that small and even large businesses faces and which impede productivity. Many workers were dissatisfied with their jobs because they were under pressure to pay bills on a limited salary. Workers' vagueness occasionally felt that they were shortchanged when they could be paid fairly. Many businesses do not appear to place a high value on their employees' job satisfaction. On the other hand, their representatives do not appear to be able to speak up for their interests because they were afraid of being demoted, harassed by their bosses, or, worse, rejected from their work.

All kinds of businesses were aware that their people were their most valuable assets. However, to get the most out of these resources—their full potential, abilities, and commitment to the job—important was to regularly be assessed how productively they were working within their companies and to kept inspiring them to reach those goals. Employee dedication to their profession or career was frequently the result of their motivation (Chu & Kuo, 2015).

Employees who consistently exhibit high levels of efficacy, output, and output efficiency were said to be productive. They were dedicated to attaining their objectives and made a substantial contribution to the accomplishments of their organization. Today, institutions were doing their best to lessen employee turnover and increase productivity of employees. Hence, it was one of the major goals of each company to improve commitment, satisfaction, teamwork, and training to obtain a win-win situation between them and their employees.

Previous research has demonstrated that employee work engagement could enhance their participation and stimulate their best performance, thus supporting organizational goals. Work engagement was a condition whereby an individual has a positive and fulfilling attitude toward their duties, and was characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. In this context, vigor was defined as a high level of energy while working, whereas dedication was denoted strong involvement in one's work and absorption refers to being concentrated and happy while working (Lee et al., 2017).

The obligation of laborers' inclusion in their affiliation was referred to as representative responsibility (Wainwright, 2018). Overall, laborers who were centered on their activity had a relationship with their organization, believed they fit in, and believed they understood the organization's goals. The additional assessment of such a workforce was that they would, for the most part, be consistently chosen in their work, demonstrated moderately high productivity, and were increasingly proactive in offering their assistance (Wainwright,

2018).

As a result, positive behaviors that benefited the organization and other employees were displayed. When an employee perceived their working environment to be unfavorable, they retaliated by engaging in negative behaviors or threatening to quit. Job satisfaction was one of the important factors that has piqued the interest of both organizational managers and academy members. Though there was no conclusive evidence that job satisfaction directly affects productivity because productivity was dependent on so many variables, it remained a top priority for managers. Job satisfaction was defined as an individual's positive mental attitude toward his or her job. "A happy employee was a productive employee," as the saying goes. Job satisfaction was critical because most people spent a significant portion of their lives at work. Moreover, job satisfaction had an impact on employees' personal lives as well, because a satisfied employee was a contented and happy human being. A highly satisfied employee had better physical and mental health (George, 2017).

Despite the number of studies highlighting the importance of employee job satisfaction, many existing businesses continued to ignore, if not downplayed, the issue. As a result, the investigator aimed to provide businesses with evidence-based tactics that would enable them to fully be utilized the potential of their staff, guaranteeing enduring productivity increased and encouraging a culture of continual development in the sake of achieving organizational excellence. The research along the lines attempted to determine the worker's level of duty and occupation fulfillment that inspired the representative to become increasingly profitable and effective in their duty. It also investigated the most important factors that influenced employee productivity. With the following objectives, the study would assist the administration in retaining the pool of talents in this generation's organization.

Methodology

The study described the following: the appropriate research design, the locale and its geographical location, the selection of participants and its sampling process, the accurate research tool, the data collection procedure, and the appropriate statistical treatment appropriate in answering all hypotheses.

Research Design

Because this study collected information on employees' commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, training, and productivity, the descriptive correlational and causal research design was used. It was descriptive because the investigator chose to study a specific phenomenon in which the relationship of variability was being considered. A descriptive study aimed to characterize a phenomenon and its traits. This study was more interested in what occurred than how or why it happened (Nasajji, 2015). Although the data in this type of study may be gathered qualitatively, it was frequently statistically examined, with relationships been found using statistics like frequencies, percentages, and averages.

Nair (2021) said that a technique for determining the cause-and-effect relationship between a dependent and an independent variable was causal-comparative research. This relationship was typically only suggested because we cannot completely control an independent variable. As a result, the study was descriptive. Rather than conducting an experiment, examined the relationships between various variables in which the independent variable already exists. It also established whether independent variables have a direct influence on the dependent variable and why.

This included determining the causes of specific occurrences (or non-occurrences). A causal-comparative study's primary goal was to investigate effects, consequences, and causes— additional features of comparative causal studies that do not select participants at random to save time and money.

Participants

Employees from 3 campuses were randomly selected, particularly faculty and staff who had served for at least five (5) mos. in Liceo de Cagayan University and were encouraged to voluntarily participate in this study.

The purposive sampling procedure was utilized in getting the sample of the study as it purposefully needed rank-and-file and faculty employees working in any of the University's departments as participants.

Instruments

A five-part questionnaire was used in this study. The first, second and fifth section were carefully adapted from the study of Geroy (2020) and modified to suit the specific needs of the population, entitled "Commitment, Job Satisfaction, and Productivity of Employees in a Higher Education Institution." The third and fourth part were self-made descriptive survey questionnaires using a Likert-like scale.

Procedure

The investigator sent a letter of consent to the Dean of the School of Business, Management, and Accountancy. A letter of approval to conduct the study by the Vice President of Research, Publication and Extension Vice President of Academic Affairs was sought. Then, a letter of consent sent to the President of the University, as well as to the Vice President for Academic Affairs of the institution to conduct the study. To ensure the quality and reliability of research findings, the investigator observed the following: (a) the investigator sought approval from the adviser after careful assessment and review of the manuscript for the project paper and (b) wrote

letters and secured permission to conduct the study, following the Research Ethics Board (REB) informed consent form for a more reliable and valid study and its results. Regarding the risk and confidentiality of the data gathered, the investigator assured the participants that all information gathered from them would be dealt with with utmost confidentiality and security of the information. The investigator gave the participants first the information about what the study was all about and how it should be answered. The participants finished answering the survey questionnaire within 3 to 5 minutes only as it was in the Likert Scale scoring system for their convenience. Creating a consent document for research participants was one part of the informed consent process. The primary purpose of the consent document was to provide information to prospective research participants that enabled them to give free and informed consent to participate in research. Consent documents conformed to standards created to support understandability and voluntariness. Responses then were coded, tallied, and collated in tables for purposes of statistical treatment and do the data analysis. Proper scaling was also used for the independent variables.

Data Ana

Descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, were employed to summarize the data collected for Problems 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5. Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in answering the statement of problem number six (6). Multiple Regression Analysis was utilized to identify the variables that best predict employees' productivity, for the statement of the problem seven (7).

Results and Discussion

The findings of the study are summarized as follows:

The first statement of the problem investigated the level of employees' commitment, in terms of service commitment, work commitment, and company commitment. It claimed that the employees agree and are committed to the overall mean score of $M=4.20$. The indicator "Customer satisfaction is a priority in the department" has the highest mean of 4.46 under service commitment. This clearly implies that the workers show a greater degree of dedication to service-related tasks than to regular work and company obligations.

The second statement of the problem looked at the level of job satisfaction of employees in terms of responsibility, recognition, professional development, physical working condition, job security/pay, and working relationship. The study revealed that the employees were satisfied with their job. The overall mean score is $M=3.97$ described as agree and interpreted as satisfied that shows a degree of contentment among workers in all areas of their workplace. Employees show satisfaction with their roles in terms of responsibility, indicating that they find them meaningful and satisfying. Another important factor is recognition, which gives workers a sense of respect and value for their work. The data also shows that employees are satisfied with their professional development, indicating that they value the organization's provision of growth and skill-enhancement opportunities. Employee satisfaction with the physical working conditions indicates that they are comfortable and well-cared for in the workplace. In the level of employees' job satisfaction in terms of responsibility, the indicator "My job allows me to take on challenging tasks and projects" has the highest mean score of $M=4.38$.

The third statement of the problem measured the level of employees' teamwork in terms of team trust, rewards and recognition, and dedication. The data revealed that the employees are satisfied with the overall mean score is $M=3.95$, described as agree and interpreted as satisfied. In terms of teamwork, the results show a high degree of employee satisfaction, especially when it comes to team trust, rewards and recognition, and dedication. When it comes to team trust, workers show faith and confidence in one another, which promotes a supportive and cooperative work atmosphere. Incentives and recognition are important as well; workers express satisfaction when their contributions are recognized and valued. This shows that staff members are not only cooperative but also have a shared interest in the team's and the company's overall success. In the level employees' teamwork in terms of Dedication, the indicator "The department ensures that everyone on the office shows positivity towards another" has the highest mean score of $M=4.16$.

The fourth statement of the problem investigated the level of employees' training in terms of seminar, workshop, and skills development. Findings showed that the employees were satisfied with the overall mean score is $M=3.96$, described as agree and interpreted as satisfied. The findings show that employees are satisfied with training, which includes seminars, workshops, and skill development. Regarding seminars, staff members are happy, indicating that these events—which are frequently organized in collaboration with HR—are successful and well-liked. The positive attitude also extends to workshops, suggesting that workers find these more interactive and hands-on learning opportunities valuable and satisfying.

Moreover, workers express contentment with skill enhancement, underscoring the effectiveness and recognition of the company's endeavors to augment their competencies and expertise. The overwhelmingly positive feedback regarding training indicates that workers view these chances as worthwhile, which helps them grow professionally and feel satisfied at work overall. In the level of employees' training in terms of seminar, the indicator "Training seminars are often handled by the HR Department and in partnership with the department" has the highest mean score of $M=4.15$.

The fifth problem investigated the level of the employees' productivity. The study revealed that the employees were productive with an overall mean score is $M=3.95$, described as agree and interpreted as productive. The findings show a high degree of worker

productivity, indicating that workers actively contribute to the completion of assignments and organizational objectives. The results of the study show that there is a productive and happy workforce with consistently engaged workers who successfully complete their tasks. The study's findings regarding commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training, among other things, may be responsible for this productivity and demonstrate a productive and dynamic work environment. All things considered; the data show a flourishing workplace where workers are not only content but actively assisting the organization in achieving its goals through their hard work. In the level of the employees' productivity, the indicator "Department personnel are keen to reducing the number of customer complaints" has the highest mean score of $M=4.06$.

The sixth problem investigated the possibility of a correlation between commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training. Findings revealed that variables; employees' productivity and employees' commitment ($r = .578$), employees job satisfaction ($r = .723$), and employees' teamwork ($r = .774$), and employees training ($r = .715$) have a positive significant correlation/relationship to employees' productivity. This can be further interpreted that if these variables increase, employees' productivity will also increase.

The study finds that employees' productivity is positively and significantly correlated with commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training. This correlation suggests that workers' productivity will rise in tandem with increases in commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training levels. Put another way, these factors are related, and higher levels of dedication, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training are linked to higher levels of productivity overall. This research offers organizations important new information by indicating that deliberate initiatives to improve teamwork, commitment, job satisfaction, and training can act as powerful catalysts to increase worker output and advance organizational objectives.

On problem 7, using multiple linear regression, it has been confirmed that the best predictor/influencer of employees' productivity is skills development ($\beta=.355$) followed by dedication ($\beta=.277$), Team Trust ($\beta=.139$), Recognition ($\beta=.111$), and Physical Working Condition ($\beta=.090$). Therefore, these predictors can be used to reject the null hypothesis. According to the study, investing in the development of employees' skills has the biggest positive influence on overall productivity, making it the most significant predictor of workers' productivity. After skill development, commitment, team trust, acknowledgment, and physical workspace conditions are also important predictors, albeit to differing extents. These show that several elements, such as workers' dedication, faith in the group, recognition of their efforts, and comfortable working environments, all work together to create a highly productive workforce. These results provide insightful information for companies looking to maximize output through deliberate attention to skill development and the development of a positive, encouraging work environment.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are hereby drawn:

The employees in higher education institutions are committed in terms of service commitment, work commitment, and company commitment. They demonstrate their dedication by making customer satisfaction a priority and acknowledging it as a key value within their department. Their commitment and feeling of purpose are highlighted by their strong conviction that their work has a significant impact on the institution and its stakeholders.

There is a noticeable high degree of employee satisfaction in demonstrating the institution's faith in its employees, the chance to take on difficult assignments and projects that promote professional development and a sense of purpose. They are very satisfied with how they are handling their responsibilities.

Employees are satisfied with their teamwork in each department particularly in team trust, rewards and recognition, and dedication. The emphasis on encouraging positivity towards one another contributes significantly to the establishment of a cohesive and effective teamwork culture.

The employees are highly satisfied in terms of seminar, workshop, and skills development. This is demonstrated by the collaborative approach to training, which involves seminars jointly led by the HR Department and the respective departments. In addition to improving individual abilities, this shared commitment to professional development also promotes a sense of solidarity and support.

The employees are productive and the evident dedication of department personnel to minimizing customer complaints is a testament to the institution's commitment to employee productivity.

There is a significant relationship between employees' productivity and commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training. High level of commitment, satisfaction, teamwork, and training results to employees' productivity.

Skills development, dedication, team trust, recognition, and physical working conditions predict employees' productivity in higher education institution. The group of predictors collectively and resoundingly reject the null hypothesis, demonstrating that deliberate investments in skill development, dedication, team trust, recognition, and physical working conditions can positively impact workers' productivity.

The following recommendations are suggested considering the abovementioned findings and conclusions. These recommendations may help the Higher Education Institutions, administrators, and other research scholars conduct programs that specifically address

employee's productivity, which deleteriously impacts employees' well-being and organizational success. Based on the relevant findings and conclusions of the study previously mentioned, the following recommendations are presented:

Department of Labor and Employment. This government agency may create seminars and symposia in various organizations, both public and private, which may help educate management and employees alike on the importance of employee commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, and training to boost their respective organization's efficiency. These occasions may also let the DOLE evaluate which companies are upholding (or violating) their employees' rights, which are affecting their commitment and job satisfaction, teamwork, and training. May set up continuous monitoring mechanisms to track changes in productivity and regularly assess the effectiveness of employees.

Public Agencies and Private Companies. Administrators and upper management may be able to use this study to plan programs and incentives, which may ignite their employees' commitment to the company as well as schedule evaluations among their employees regarding their job satisfaction or dissatisfaction, needed training, and effective teamwork. May offer leadership development and managerial training programs to enhance leadership skills and promote effective team management. Also, agencies and companies may upgrade technological infrastructure and provide training programs to equip employees with the skills necessary to leverage new tools effectively.

Human Resource Management. HR staff may use this research as a basis on how to improve their organization's system to gain committed and satisfied employees, well trained, and bolster teamwork within the organization which, in turn, increases the company's productivity. HR staff is encouraged to acknowledge and capitalize on the positive fit between employees' roles and their sense of purpose in the workplace.

Employed workers. Employees may be able to peruse this research as an evaluative way of learning on how to assess the specific factors that may affect their commitment, job satisfaction, and productivity, needed training and proper teamwork that strengthen interpersonal relationships, improve collaboration, and foster a sense of unity among co-workers.

Higher Education Institutions. Professors and instructors of the various programs under the Master in Business Administration and Doctor in Management major in Leadership and Organization may utilize this study as a local educational tool in teaching their students on the significant relationships of commitment, job satisfaction, training, and teamwork, and productivity.

Students might enhance their knowledge based on the importance of commitment, job satisfaction, teamwork, training, and productivity among today's employees. Target effective training programs to improve and learn and make sure the programs are well-organized, cooperative, and in line with the needs of their professional development.

Liceo De Cagayan University may establish a system for ongoing monitoring and evaluation of employee satisfaction, particularly regarding salary and may regularly reassess the effectiveness of implemented changes and adjust as necessary where salary satisfaction is reported to be only moderately satisfied compared to other variables.

For the future researcher who wants to investigate the dynamics of workers' productivity, may obtain a deeper understanding of the contextual factors influencing the relationship between teamwork, training, and productivity. They may delve deeper into the identified factors influencing employee's productivity in higher education institutions by exploring additional variables and investigate their relationships and impact on productivity.

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